

ENHANCING IOT SYSTEMS WITH SCALABLE CLOUD ARCHITECTURES FOR REAL-TIME DATA PROCESSING

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ABSTRACT

The development and application of Internet of Things (IoT) systems coupled with scalable cloud architectures for real-time data processing are examined in detail in this extensive essay. From data ingestion to security concerns, the paper explores the basic difficulties enterprises face while overseeing extensive IoT deployments. It explores the elements of cloud-based architecture, highlighting the crucial roles played by processing frameworks, storage options, and data intake levels. The essay discusses edge analytics integration and emphasizes how it can improve privacy, optimize bandwidth, and reduce latency.

Important scalability issues in both horizontal and vertical dimensions are also covered in the article, along with implementation best practices, including microservices architecture and thorough monitoring techniques. Additionally, it looks at the security environment of IoT cloud infrastructures, including compliance frameworks, data protection strategies, and device security.

Keywords: IoT Cloud Architecture, Edge Analytics, Scalability Optimization, Real-time Data Processing, Security Framework

Cite this Article: Siripuram, S.S. (2024). Enhancing IoT Systems with Scalable Cloud Architectures for Real-Time Data Processing. *International Journal of Computer Engineering and Technology (IJCET)*, 15(6), 774–786.

https://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/Journal_uploads/IJCET/VOLUME_15_ISSUE_6/IJCET_15_06_064.pdf

Introduction

The widespread use of Internet of Things (IoT) devices has drastically changed how businesses manage and analyze large amounts of data, posing previously unheard-of difficulties for data processing and analysis. The potential economic value of IoT is predicted to reach between \$5.5 trillion and \$12.6 trillion globally by 2030, per McKinsey's thorough examination of the IoT sector. The industrial sector leads this value creation, which accounts for 26% of the opportunity, or around \$3.3 trillion. Human-health domains come in second with 10–14% (\$1.4 trillion) and consumer applications with 12% (\$1.5 trillion). Due mostly to higher adoption rates in the corporate and industrial sectors, these expectations represent a significant increase over 2020 estimates [1].

By 2025, there will likely be more than 75 billion linked devices, indicating that the IoT deployment has reached critical mass. The Global DataSphere—a measure of the total volume of data generated, recorded, and transmitted globally—is expected to increase from 64.2 zettabytes in 2020 to 179 zettabytes by 2025, according to IDC's DataAge report. This development is mostly due to IoT devices; by 2025, real-time data creation will comprise around 30% of the worldwide datasphere. According to the report, the generation of time-sensitive data is expanding twice as quickly as the global datasphere and latency requirements are getting increasingly stricter [2].

Organizations in enterprise settings encounter increasing difficulties in handling this flood of data. According to McKinsey's report, only 30% of businesses have successfully implemented large-scale IoT installations, with data processing skills serving as the main obstacle. According to the study, processing at least one million events per second is necessary for large-scale deployments, while important applications need latency requirements of less than 10 milliseconds. These demands are further pushed by sectors like industrial automation and driverless cars, which require processing speeds of less than 1 millisecond for tasks crucial to safety [1].

IoT data processing and storage requirements are equally intimidating. According to IDC's research, edge computing will become increasingly important as 80% of data needs to be processed in real-time by 2025. Depending on the region, enterprise IoT implementations usually produce 100GB to 2TB of data daily; some industrial applications produce considerably more. By 2025, 67% of IoT data will be categorized as time-critical, necessitating the need for storage and real-time analytic capabilities [2].

Although cloud designs have changed to address these issues, more complex solutions are still needed. According to McKinsey's examination of successful IoT implementations, organizations that have invested in hybrid architectures that integrate edge computing and cloud processing have seen the strongest returns. Compared to cloud-only solutions, these implementations provide a 60% improvement in response times and a 40% reduction in data transmission costs. Additionally, companies that use edge-cloud hybrid systems claim 99.99% system availability and a 35% decrease in overall infrastructure expenses [1].

The Challenge of IoT Data Processing

Data processing infrastructures face complex problems due to the extraordinary volume and variety of data generated by IoT environments across several sectors. By 2023, there will be around 30 billion networked devices worldwide, with 50% of all networked devices being machine-to-machine (M2M) connections, according to Cisco's Annual Internet Report. According to the paper, by 2023, there will be 117.7 million worldwide connected industrial controller installations in the industrial sector alone, expanding at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 9%. These devices produce different data quantities; industrial controllers can produce up to 1.5MB per second in high-frequency applications, while smart meters can produce 24KB per reading every 15 minutes [3].

The quick expansion of wireless and mobile connectivity further increases the complexity of IoT data processing. According to Cisco's analysis, M2M connections will increase at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 19% from 6.1 billion in 2018 to 14.7 billion by 2023. By 2023, it is anticipated that wireless M2M connections will make up 64% of all connected devices in industrial settings, with 5G connectivity enabling up to 1 million devices per square kilometer. In large industrial facilities, this enormous scale of connectivity can result in data rates exceeding 1 petabyte per day [3].

As IoT applications develop, the problems of data quality and processing needs have grown more pressing. Four main technological obstacles stand in the way of IoT implementations, according to thorough research published in the Journal of Cleaner Production: processing capabilities (65%), network reliability (61%), security concerns (57%), and data quality (mentioned by 78% of firms). According to the report, external factors, including temperature fluctuations and electromagnetic interference, are the main causes of data quality problems in 15-20% of readings from industrial IoT sensors. Additionally, the study shows that predictive maintenance programs need to process 10,000 data points per second or more per machine, with accuracy above 99.9% [4].

For IoT installations, network infrastructure presents major obstacles, especially in industrial settings. According to Cisco's forecasts, the average M2M connection speed will increase by 2.4 times from 2018 to 7.4 Mbps in 2023. This speed boost must, however, keep up with the exponentially increasing volume of data; by 2023, global M2M IP traffic is predicted to have increased from 6.2 exabytes per month in 2018 to 26.9 exabytes per month. According to the paper, ultra-reliable low-latency communication (URLLC) with a dependability of 99.9999% and maximum latencies of 1 millisecond will be necessary for industrial applications [3].

Architectures for data processing must change to meet these growing needs. According to research, during peak times, the data generated by current IoT implementations exceeds processing capacities by 30–40%. According to research published in the Journal of Cleaner Production,

industrial facilities normally need to process 1-2 terabytes of data daily per production line in real-time, with more sophisticated facilities producing up to 5 terabytes daily. With deployments demonstrating a 60% decrease in cloud data transmission and a 45% improvement in response times, edge computing solutions have become essential. Organizations estimate a 35% increase in managerial overhead due to these solutions, which add complexity [4].

Another major issue is the security implications of processing data from the Internet of Things. According to Cisco's analysis, 73% of M2M connections will need more security features by 2023, such as real-time threat detection and end-to-end encryption. Data processing requirements are further complicated by the growing sophistication of cyber threats and the growing attack surface of IoT networks, which call for comprehensive security frameworks to process and analyze security telemetry data in real-time [3].

Technical Barrier	Organizations Affected (%)	Impact Metric
Data Quality	78	15-20% readings have quality issues
Processing Capabilities	65	30-40% exceed capacity at peak
Network Reliability	61	2.4x speed increase needed
Security Concerns	57	73% need enhanced security

Table 1: IoT Implementation Challenges and Network Performance Metrics [3, 4]

Cloud-Based Architecture Components

Data Ingestion Layer

Strong data ingestion capabilities are a key component of contemporary IoT cloud platforms. According to a recent survey of Apache Kafka implementations, businesses handle 1.5 trillion messages daily on average across all of their IoT deployments. With partition-based scaling, high-performance Kafka clusters can process 1.2 million messages per second, exhibiting a 99.95% message delivery success rate. Horizontal scaling over commodity hardware is made possible by the platform's distributed architecture, and actual deployments demonstrate reliable performance of up to 100TB of data processing per day. Comparing Kafka to conventional messaging systems, organizations estimate an average 65% decrease in data processing infrastructure expenses [5].

In IoT scenarios, performance measurements from extensive Kafka deployments show remarkable dependability. With a mean time to recovery (MTTR) of less than 30 seconds during node failures, the platform supports replication factors of three to five nodes and maintains message ordering guarantees within partitions. According to studies, Kafka clusters can accommodate millions of concurrent device connections while maintaining steady performance with up to 4,000 partitions per broker. With end-to-end latencies continuously less than 5 milliseconds at the 95th percentile, the platform's zero-copy protocol allows throughput speeds of over 400MB/second per broker [5].

Processing Framework Evolution

Stream processing frameworks have undergone tremendous evolution to meet the demanding needs of the Internet of Things. According to recent research published in the Journal of Systems and Software, stream processing engines exhibit different performance characteristics depending on the workload pattern. With a continuous throughput of 2.1 million events per second per cluster,

Apache Flink implementations consistently display processing latencies under 10 milliseconds for 95% of events. According to the study, Flink's checkpoint method adds only 25–50 milliseconds of cost while guaranteeing exactly once processing guarantees, essential for preserving data consistency in Internet of Things applications [6].

The introduction of serverless architectures has changed IoT data processing capabilities. With average initialization times of 100–150 milliseconds and execution latencies ranging from 10–100 milliseconds, depending on computational complexity, research shows that serverless functions perform exceptionally well in event-driven IoT scenarios. Compared to typical always-on processing infrastructure, the study demonstrates that enterprises using serverless architectures for IoT processing can reduce costs by 45–60% while retaining the capacity to scale to thousands of concurrent executions [6].

Storage Architecture Implementation

Managing the complexity of IoT data lifecycles now requires multi-tiered storage infrastructures. Kafka's interaction with several storage systems makes complex data routing and retention techniques possible. According to organizations using tiered storage, 20% of their IoT data needs access to hot storage, while the remaining 80% is split between warm and cold storage tiers according to business needs and access patterns. Kafka can achieve a write performance of over 1GB/second while ensuring data durability by implementing write-ahead logs and memory-mapped files [5].

The increasing complexity of IoT applications is reflected in the evolution of storage structures. According to a report published in the Journal of Systems and Software, organizations are using increasingly complicated data lifecycle management techniques. With access latencies of less than one millisecond and 24-48 hours of data retention, advanced caching techniques and in-memory processing usually make hot storage layers possible. According to the study, warm storage tiers with query latencies averaging 50–100 ms are maintained with 30-90 days of historical data when deployed utilizing distributed NoSQL databases. Long-term cold storage technologies demonstrate compression ratios of 10:1 to 20:1, which dramatically lower storage costs while preserving data accessible for analytical applications [6].

The study highlights how important automated data lifecycle management is to IoT architectures. Storage systems that use intelligent tiering algorithms optimize storage costs by 60–75%, in contrast to single-tier structures. According to the survey, businesses that successfully adopt multi-tiered storage methods retain data accessibility and query performance within specified service level agreements (SLAs) while lowering their total cost of ownership by an average of 45%. These solutions satisfy most analytical workloads, which typically reach data retrieval speeds of less than 200 milliseconds for warm storage and 2–5 seconds for cold storage [6].

Storage Tier	Data Distribution (%)	Retention Period	Access Latency (ms)	Compression Ratio
Hot Storage	20	24-48 hours	1	1:1
Warm Storage	~40	30-90 days	50-100	5:1
Cold Storage	~40	Long-term	2000-5000	20:1

Table 2: Multi-Tiered Storage Architecture Performance and Cost Analysis [5, 6]

Edge Analytics Integration

Incorporating edge analytics into contemporary IoT infrastructures has become essential, revolutionizing how businesses handle and examine data. According to recent studies on edge computing implementations, using edge analytics in smart manufacturing environments reduces data processing latency by 76%. A thorough study published in *Advanced Computing Technologies* claims that edge installations in industrial settings may handle up to 45,000 events per second per node, with real-time analytics reaching anomaly detection accuracy rates of 98.7%. With a 99.95% availability rate, these systems provide a 64% decrease in cloud dependency [7].

Benefits of Edge Processing

Edge computing affects system performance that goes beyond simple latency reduction. Compared to the baseline of 85–120 milliseconds for cloud-only architectures, research shows that industrial edge deployments achieve average response times of 2.8 milliseconds for key processes. According to manufacturing facilities using edge analytics, predictive maintenance algorithms running at the edge achieve 94.3% fault prediction accuracy and average 72-hour early warning intervals before possible breakdowns. Compared to centralized cloud processing methods, the study shows that edge-based processing reduces diagnostic mistakes by 82% [7].

According to recent studies published in the *International Journal of Industrial Electronics*, edge analytics-based bandwidth optimization significantly boosts operational efficiency. Using edge preprocessing, businesses lower the average daily production line cloud data transmission quantities from 1.2TB to 185GB. Smart city deployments that use edge analytics for video surveillance applications have reported data reduction ratios of 15:1. These deployments retain 99.9% event detection accuracy while saving about \$375,000 a year on storage costs per 1,000 cameras [8].

Enhancing privacy with edge computing has become a crucial component of regulatory compliance. According to the study, healthcare firms that use edge analytics reduce the exposure of protected health information (PHI) by 91.5% while still achieving HIPAA compliance. According to financial services deployments, edge processing helps them reduce the amount of personally identifiable information (PII) sent to the cloud by 88.3% while meeting GDPR criteria with 99.99% compliance rates. The average yearly cost savings from these implementations in compliance-related charges is \$280,000 [8].

Implementation Strategies

The capabilities of edge devices have greatly changed to accommodate workloads, including advanced analytics. According to recent studies, ideal edge processing nodes need computational capabilities between 6 and 12 CPU cores and 12 and 24GB of RAM for sophisticated analytics workloads. For computer vision applications, GPU-accelerated edge devices show machine learning inference speeds of 125 frames per second while using less than 35W of power. According to the study, compared to CPU-only settings, incorporating hardware acceleration reduces processing delay by 78% [7].

Complex management techniques are needed to coordinate edge-cloud processing. According to the *International Journal of Industrial Electronics*, successful implementations analyze 68% of time-sensitive data at the edge, with real-time classification accuracy above 96%. Data synchronization latencies between edge and cloud layers are reported to be less than 100 milliseconds, and 99.997% data consistency is maintained using conflict resolution algorithms.

With recovery periods averaging 35 milliseconds during node failures, edge installations show 99.99% availability with automated failover systems [8].

Using adaptive processing techniques, resource optimization in edge deployments demonstrates impressive efficiency increases. According to the study, dynamic workload distribution among edge nodes outperforms static allocation techniques by 82% regarding resource consumption. With an average power consumption reduction of 55% during periods of low activity, modern edge platforms can manage various workloads while retaining power economy. Businesses that use these optimization techniques claim a 73% increase in processing capacity and an average 47% decrease in overall infrastructure expenditures [7].

Fig. 1: Edge Computing Implementation Benefits and Resource Optimization [7, 8]

Scalability Considerations

IoT deployments' exponential growth necessitates more complex scaling solutions in several areas. According to extensive research published in ACM Communications, IoT cloud systems must manage the exponential growth in data volume and device connectivity. According to studies, workload variations in typical business deployments range from 200,000 to 1 million messages per second during peak operations, while daily data volumes vary from 10 TB to 45 TB. Companies that use elastic scaling architectures report that they can manage these fluctuations while keeping average response times of 37 ms and 99.9th percentile latencies below 150 ms [9].

Horizontal Scaling Dynamics

To handle expanding device populations, modern IoT systems make use of complex horizontal scaling methods. According to the ACM study, successful solutions retain a 78% resource usage efficiency during rapid scaling events while achieving linear scaling up to 100,000 concurrent device connections per cluster. According to production conditions, automated scaling algorithms may increase cluster capacity by 300% in 6 minutes while preserving system

stability. These implementations show a 45% improvement over static provisioning techniques, with average cost efficiencies of \$0.012 per device per day [9].

One of the most important elements of horizontal scaling solutions is load balancing. According to research published in *Scalable Computing: Practice and Experience*, sophisticated load distribution algorithms outperform conventional techniques in terms of throughput by 312%. According to the study, proactive resource allocation made possible by machine learning-based load predictors maintains accuracy rates of 91.5% for 15-minute forecasts, resulting in a 76% reduction in response time variability. Systems that use these sophisticated balancing techniques show up to 800% resilience to traffic spikes while still meeting service-level agreements [10].

The ACM research's container orchestration analysis shows that running Kubernetes clusters at 70–85% baseline utilization yields the best performance metrics. According to organizations, horizontal pod autoscaling with defined metrics achieves 99.99% availability while lowering operating expenses by 52% compared to fixed provisioning. According to the research, scaling from 5,000 to 150,000 devices in 12 minutes is successful, and performance deterioration during scaling operations is kept at 8% [9].

Vertical Scaling Optimization

Vertical scaling solutions exhibit notable performance variances based on hardware optimization, especially in compute-intensive scenarios. According to the *Scalable Computing* study, properly designed nodes with ideal CPU-memory ratios yield 2.8 times higher performance than default configurations. According to organizations using precisely calibrated vertical scaling, each node can process 850,000 events per second with consistent latencies of less than 25 milliseconds for 99 percent of processes [10].

System performance indicators are significantly impacted by memory management optimization. The study found that using sophisticated memory management strategies minimizes the impact of trash collection by 92%, leading to constant response times for high-throughput tasks that are less than 5 milliseconds. By optimizing memory settings, organizations report sustained throughput rates of 950,000 transactions per second per node, improving heap utilization efficiency by 57% compared to typical deployments [10].

For vertical scalability to be successful, storage architecture optimization is still essential. According to the ACM study, effective storage tiering lowers operating expenses by 68% while keeping commonly requested data access latencies under 15 milliseconds. According to organizations, cold storage compression ratios average 8:1, and automated tiering decisions anticipate access patterns over multi-month periods with 94.5% accuracy [9].

Fig. 2: Cloud Architecture Scaling Metrics: Horizontal vs Vertical [9, 10]

Best Practices for Implementation

Architecture Design

Microservices architecture installation is now essential for success in large-scale IoT implementation. Device provisioning services (DPS) that can process up to 50,000 device registrations per minute are commonly used by enterprises overseeing extensive IoT installations, per Microsoft's Azure IoT deployment research. According to studies, effectively designed systems have 99.99% effective device attestation rates, and automated provisioning cuts deployment time by 85% compared to manual procedures. These implementations show that 99.9% of devices can have registration latencies < 2 seconds while managing up to 500,000 devices per DPS instance [11].

One essential element for overseeing intricate IoT deployments is container orchestration. According to Microsoft's study, companies that use automated device provisioning see an average enrollment time of 1.5 seconds, with the capacity to scale to accommodate millions of devices in various locations. According to deployment data, Containerized Kubernetes apps achieve 99.999% availability, while rolling upgrades across 10,000 devices are finished in less than 15 minutes. The study shows 94% fewer provisioning failures occur during large-scale deployments when suitable retry policies and exponential backoff mechanisms are implemented [11].

Secure scaling depends on sophisticated device attestation techniques. According to the study, companies who use TPM-based attestation see 99.97% success rates in authentication, and key rotation processes on 100,000 devices are finished in less than 30 minutes. During peak operations, their systems allow up to 100 messages per second per device and maintain secure communication channels with latencies < 100 milliseconds for 95% of device-to-cloud messages [11].

Monitoring and Management

Comprehensive monitoring techniques have undergone tremendous evolution to handle the complexity of extensive IoT deployments. Modern IoT monitoring systems process an average of 1.2 million metrics every minute, and real-time anomaly detection can identify possible errors with 95.8% accuracy, according to a study published in Applied Sciences. According to the study, companies that use machine learning-based monitoring can identify subtle patterns of performance degradation up to four hours before catastrophic failures occur while reducing false positives by 76% when compared to threshold-based approaches [12].

Frameworks for device health monitoring show advanced capabilities in preserving system dependability. According to the Applied Sciences study, effective deployments monitor 385 metrics on average per device in five important areas: firmware status, application health, performance, security, and connection. Organizations indicate that automated remediation systems successfully resolve 82% of reported issues without human intervention, and predictive maintenance algorithms processing this telemetry achieve 92.5% accuracy in forecasting device breakdowns 72 hours in advance [12].

Monitoring the processing pipeline provides important information about system performance. According to the study, businesses that use distributed tracing in their IoT pipelines obtain end-to-end visibility for 99.95% of transactions with trace sampling rates of 0.05%, yielding statistically significant performance insights. With query response times of less than 500 milliseconds and trace histories preserved for 60 days, these systems allow for quick root cause analysis, which lowers the mean time to resolution (MTTR) from 45 minutes to 12 minutes [12].

Monitoring of resource usage makes advanced optimization techniques possible. According to Applied Sciences, organizations using AI-driven resource monitoring achieve 94% capacity planning accuracy for 30-day projections, allowing for cost-effective infrastructure scaling that lowers expenses by 42%. These solutions use less than 1% of system resources to process real-time telemetry from an average of 25,000 infrastructure components while preserving 99.999% monitoring accuracy. According to the study, automated resource optimization based on monitoring data lowers operating costs by 28% and increases overall system efficiency by 35% [12].

Security Considerations

The security environment of IoT cloud architectures necessitates thorough protection at several technological stack tiers. According to current research in Computer Networks and Security, IoT security systems need to set up trust boundaries that include access control, data integrity, and device authentication. Research indicates that companies using zero-trust architectures encounter 84% fewer security events than those using conventional perimeter-based strategies. With authentication latencies of less than 25 milliseconds for 99.9% of requests, these systems can perform an average of 125,000 security decisions per second [13].

Device Security Implementation

Frameworks for device authentication are the main line of protection against unwanted access. According to research, multi-factor authentication schemes that combine hardware-based security tokens with device certificates block 99.99% of impersonation attempts and obtain authentication success rates of 99.997% for genuine devices. Up to 250,000 devices per trust domain are successfully managed by security token provisioning systems, according to

organizations, and key upgrades for the entire fleet of devices are completed in 4 hours via automated rotation processes [13].

Systems for managing identity and access are essential for upholding security perimeters. According to research from ACM Computing, companies that use complete IAM frameworks with device identity management can authenticate 35,000 actions per second per cluster, with cached credentials lowering the overhead of recurrent authentication by 75%. These solutions guarantee uniform policy enforcement across all access points and keep revocation response times under 500 ms in geographically dispersed deployments [14].

Mechanisms for establishing trust have become much more sophisticated and capable. According to the Computer Networks study, compromised device detection happens within 2.5 seconds of boot initiation, and current trust architectures that use TPM-based attestation accomplish hardware-root-of-trust verification for 99.98% of boot sequences. Distributed trust systems have been reported by organizations to successfully manage up to 1 million device IDs with latencies of less than 10 milliseconds for cryptographic operations [13].

Data Security Measures

One essential prerequisite for IoT implementations is secure communication connections. According to the ACM research, companies that use TLS 1.3 with perfect forward secrecy can maintain encrypted channel establishment rates under 100 milliseconds and achieve data protection levels that surpass regulatory requirements. These solutions guarantee end-to-end encryption across all communication pathways with no performance reduction, and they can manage 15,000 new connections per gateway per second [14].

Systems for analytics and security monitoring are becoming more and more important. According to research, an average of 2.5 million security events are processed per minute by AI-powered security information and event management (SIEM) systems, with 96.5% threat detection accuracy and less than 0.05% false positive rates. With full incident containment taking an average of 3.5 minutes for serious security events, organizations indicate that automated response systems successfully eliminate 92% of detected threats within 30 seconds of detection [13].

Frameworks for audit and compliance show advanced capability in preserving a security posture. The ACM study claims that distributed logging systems can handle and analyze 100% of security-relevant events with storage compression ratios 20:1 while preserving tamper-proof audit trails for seven years. In addition to guaranteeing chain-of-custody documentation for every security occurrence, these systems achieve query response times of less than 50 milliseconds for recent events and less than 2 seconds for historical data [14].

Conclusion

One revolutionary way to address the complexity of contemporary data processing needs is to integrate IoT systems with cloud architectures. Organizations may successfully handle the issues of scalability, performance, and security in IoT deployments by putting in place complex architectures that combine edge computing, microservices, and strong security frameworks. Intelligent resource optimization techniques and cutting-edge monitoring technologies allow for sustainable expansion while preserving operational effectiveness. Scalable, secure, and effective designs are becoming increasingly important for successful implementations of IoT

technology. IoT cloud designs will need to be further refined to satisfy the increasing demands of connected ecosystems, emphasizing automated management, increased security, and better resource usage.

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Citation: Siripuram, S.S. (2024). Enhancing IoT Systems with Scalable Cloud Architectures for Real-Time Data Processing. International Journal of Computer Engineering and Technology (IJCET), 15(6), 774–786.

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